

INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP AND SPORTS PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY AMONG NATIONAL PLAYERS IN PAKISTAN

Muhammad Ashraf Javed

PhD Scholar, Preston University Islamabad, Pakistan, ashrafpsaf@gmail.com

Dr. Muhammad Amin

Assistant Professor, Preston University Islamabad, Pakistan

Abstract

Study aims to investigate the impact of inclusive leadership on sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Inclusive leadership has been identified as an important element that increases sports performance with the mediating effects of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Inclusive leadership reinforces to employees' psychological safety and freedom of expression to achieve sports performance through innovative work behaviour. Literature review revealed that the relationship between inclusive leadership and performance has been investigated with the various other mediating variables in the fields of banks, education, and health sectors. However, its exploration in the field of sports industry has not yet been explored to find the effect of inclusive leadership on sports performance with the mediating effects of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Study opted snowball sampling and data was collected from 385 sports players of national level playing under the patronage of Pakistan sports industry comprising of Pakistan Sports Board (PSB) and Pakistan Cricket Board (PCB). Hypotheses of the study were formulated after identifying research objectives and questions of the study. Social Exchange Theory (SET) was used to investigate the impact of inclusive leadership in increasing sports performance through innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used for multivariate statistical analysis to examine structural relationships. Smart PLS was used for evaluating validity and the reliability of the data. Variance-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was assessed using the partial least squares path modeling method. Results and outcomes of the study contribute to enhance the sports performance at national and international competitions and provide guidelines to formulate policies for improving performance of the Pakistan sports industry. Study was restricted to Pakistan sports industry with cross sectional time horizon, whereas other industries may also be researched with the same variables and longitudinal time horizon.

Keywords: *Inclusive Leadership, Innovative Work Behaviour, Pakistan Sport Board, Psychological Safety, Sports Performance*

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Sports have been identified as an integral part of humanity and play a critical role in the development of national identity, cultural promotion, and development of nations (Jiang, 2024). Sports develop healthy entertainment and leisure time activities along with creating sense of responsibility, courage, discipline, sense of unity and leadership qualities in sports players (Rodriguez & Rodrik, 2000). Researchers have verified that sports create coordination amongst different world cultures to improve physical health of the individuals and incorporation of their diverse social values (Yilmaz & Dertli, 2025). Sports are source for development of tourism and social connections between players of diverse backgrounds (Jiang, 2024). Sports industry of the country not only provides entertainment to everyone but also acts as a powerful foundation for economic development of the country through exploitation of advanced technologies in the different fields of sports. (Şimşek & Devecioğlu, 2025).

Pakistan sports industry encompasses Pakistan Sports Board (PSB) and Pakistan Cricket Board (PCB) for managing and implementation of sports at grassroots, national and international level. PSB was established in 1962 to promote sports at grassroot level and to create public association with sports. In 1977, PSB was sited under the Ministry of Culture, Sports, and tourism. Later in 2011, its control was delegated to Ministry of Inter Provincial Coordination (MIPC) through eighteenth amendment. Pakistan Cricket Board (PCB) was instituted on 01 May 1949 as the Board of Control for Cricket in Pakistan (BCCP).

One of most important elements of sports is to develop positive youth development (PYD) and it presents an effective platform for improving children' social skills, teamwork obligations, building of character and improvement of interactive skills (Erdilnita & Ma'mun, 2024). Sports develop the cognitive abilities of individuals for better understanding of sports skills (Tokay & Akil, 2025). Hamburg declaration of IOC in 2023 defines that sports not only provide a stage for conduct of international competitions but also organize the concept of common respect, friendships, and integration of distinct values amongst sports players. Sports play a vital part in enhancing public health, community environment, physical activities and public health through economic evolution, equality of genders and attachment of various groups of different origins (Campillo-Sánchez et al., 2025).

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

Pakistan's sports industry performance at Asian games and Olympics has always been poor due to lack of sports leadership vision and development of sports policies and necessary sports infrastructures. It is also mentioned that unsuitable leadership of sports industry has badly affected the sports industry because of poor sports knowledge, absence of education, political gravities, misappropriation of funds, bribery, favoritism, personal likings, and partial selection of players (Krambia Kapardis & Levi, 2023). United Nations Development Program (UNDP) has informed that only 7% Pakistani youth take part in sports due to non-availability of sports facilities, and 93% youth have no approach to available

sports facilities. Non-availability of sports facilities is a source of disappointment between youth and belligerence in the public (Khan et al., 2024). Toxic leadership brutally influences the sports performance of influential sports through its effect on the psychological health, motivation, and performance of the populations. Various Olympians have also reinforced the presence of toxic leadership in the sports associations and develop lethal cultures for degradation of sports performances (Lundqvist et al., 2025). In Asian Games 2023 at China, Pakistan earned only 03 medals whereas Afghanistan won 05 medals and India won 107 medals.

Olympic games were launched in 1896 and Pakistan participated in 1956. Pakistan's performance at Olympic games has been enormously unfortunate and in last 69 years from 1956 to 2024 Pakistan won only eleven (11) Olympic medals (4 gold, 3 silver and 4 bronze) out of total six thousand four hundred sixty (6460) medals. Asian games started in 1951, and Pakistan in last 70 years from 1954 to 2023 won only two hundred six (206) medals (44 gold, 65 silver and 97 bronze) out of total sixteen thousand seven hundred nineteen (16719) medals.

Leadership provides vision, evaluating objectives, and developing strategies to improve organizational performance for managing their organizational goals. Sports leadership must have sports knowledge to stipulate inclusive environment in sports organizations for optimum sports performance at local and international sports competitions (Piggott et al., 2024). Ineffective leadership not only destroys sports performance but also damages image of the nation and national economy. Poor sports performance has also adversely impacted the substantial physical activities and social values of Pakistan's youth. Therefore, investigation of inclusive leaderships in the sports industry is of vital importance with the mediation effects of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Study will explain the effect of inclusive leadership on sports performance for excellence in sports performance at national and international standards.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Pakistan's constant poor performance at international sports events indicates leadership deficiencies, professional weaknesses, and limited access to sports infrastructure and facilities. Toxic and useless leadership practices have weakened athletes' motivation, psychological well-being, and overall sports performance. Therefore, there is a critical need to investigate that how inclusive leadership can improve sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety in Pakistan's sports industry.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Objectives of the study are appended below:

- a. To evaluate the direct influence of inclusive leadership on sports performance.
- b. To investigate the mediating function of innovative work behaviour between inclusive leadership and sports performance.
- c. To analyze the mediating function of psychological safety mediator between inclusive leadership and sports performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Research questions of the study are appended below:

- a. Does inclusive leadership influence sports performance?
- b. To what extent does innovative work behaviour mediate between inclusive leadership and sports performance?
- c. To what extent does psychological safety mediate between inclusive leadership and sports performance?

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Pakistan poor sports performance at national and international levels is a cause of apprehension and necessitates effective curative measures to improve sports performance through preparation of sports policies and building of sports infrastructures that meet requirements of global sports extravaganza. Sports play a crucial role in development of national identity, national soft image and culture of a country around the world through presentation of sports performances in mega sports events like Olympics, FIFA world cup, and Asian games (Murray, 2018). Sports are also used as a instrument to achieve diplomatic goals. In 1987, in pursuance of sports diplomacy, President of Pakistan Zia-ul-Haq visited India for watching cricket match to diffuse intense political situation between India and Pakistan (Mazahir et al., 2020). Sports events at an international level contribute to economy of the country and mega events are the sixth highest contributors in the economy of developed countries (Pitts, 2020; Mwamba, 2023).

National team success at international mega sport events increases patriotism, generates sense of pride in the whole nation and creates national identity to develop social integration between different groups of the national population (Nordin et al., 2023). Conduct of Mega sports events like Olympics, FIFA world cup and Asian Games, contribute billions of dollars to the economy of host country in the shape of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), rights of broadcasting, sales of tickets, contracts of sponsorships and sports tourism (Smith et al., 2023). Conducting mega sports events may also facilitate in construction of state-of-the-art stadiums and renovation of existing sports facilities. Conducting mega sports events also play a considered role in the longstanding advantages of the host country especially the host city (Ait Soussane & Ibourek, 2024). Sports diplomacy is also used by nations for sportswashing to divert the thinking of world from its social problems and political issues (Bergkvist & Skeiseid, 2024). World Health Organization (WHO) has recognized the importance of sports for augmenting public health, promoting healthier lifestyle, and improving well-being of the population through association with global sports organizations such as IOC, FIFA, and UEFA.

Effectiveness of inclusive leadership for improving performance of the organizations has not been explored in the organizations and industries with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety (Lodhi et al., 2024). This study seeks to investigate the impact of inclusive leaders in enhancing sports performance, while considering the mediating effects of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Increasing performance of players will

improve their professional expertise to achieve excellence in sports performance at national and international level sports competitions.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Sports competitions at national and international have been identified as an powerful tool for promotion of peace around the world, to develop an environment for healthy lifestyle, incorporation of diverse social values, provision of equal opportunities for worth education and to form policies for improving global public health. Quaid-i-Azam Mohammad Ali Jinnah in 1948, emphasized the importance of sports and said “Dedicate yourself to sports promotion, for when you and I are gone, leadership will go into the hands of youth, and youth is our wealth, a raw material, that must be hammered into shape for defense of the integrity and solidarity of Pakistan - the defense of the ideology of Pakistan (Ali & Rehman, 2015; Ali et al., 2024). Africa's leader, Nelson Mandela emphasized the magnitude of sports and said that "Every child has three fundamental rights, health, education, and sports (Willis, 2000). Great African leader Nelson Mandela highlighted the importance of sports that Sports has the influence to change the world as it speaks to people in a language that is understood by everyone (Marwat et al., 2020). International organizations like UN, IOC, WHO and FIFA have also highlighted the importance of sports and are using sports as an effective means to achieve UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through devising and application of global policies to achieve sustainable development in pursuance of UN 2030 agenda (Senturk, 2023; Zbiljić et al., 2025).

Professional sports are also a foundation for developing cutting-edge technologies in the country with the technology assisted training of professional players for taming their cognitive skills, decision power and enhancing sports performance at global sports competitions (Khan & Wali, 2020; Huang & Yongquan, 2025). Research scholars accept that sports industry is quite competent for moving of millions of people around the world to watch mega sports events like FIFA cup and Olympics. This mammoth move of people bolsters economy of the host country and increases social incorporation of different world populations of sports industries (Torres-Mancera, 2025; Marc, 2025).

Therefore, this study will provide constructive insights to policy makers for developing policies and strategies to formulate required infrastructures for improving sports performance at international competitions.

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY (SET)

Social Exchange Theory is an influential and significant theory for social sciences to comprehend performance of the organizations. This theory defines that when leadership exhibits positive behaviour towards employees, then in response to this positive attitude of leadership, employees perform their best to accomplish organizational performance through innovative work behaviour (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). George C. Homans is seen as the father of social exchange theory who instituted the concept in an essay of American Sociological Review in 1958 and published a book on Social Behavior in 1961 (Molm, 2015). In accordance with social exchange theory employees assume rewards and inspiration from their leadership to accomplish organizational goals (Wasono & Furinto, 2018; Ahmad et al., 2025). Social exchange theory has not been employed for evaluating sports performance in Pakistan and around the world. This study is an exploration to determine the effects of inclusive leadership on sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Study establishes the theoretical gap of previous studies carried out for determining performance of different organizations except sports performance of sports industry.

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY AND INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP

Social Exchange Theory explains that inclusive leadership develops trust among employees and creates openness in the minds of employees by proving readiness to listen and acceptability of innovative ideas. It also expresses psychological safety to employees, and it explains the impact of inclusive leadership on performance. Study model is based on social exchange theory (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Inclusive leadership believes that social exchange theory extends motivation and innovative work behaviour between leadership and employees. Scholars investigated that social exchange theory finds the influence of inclusive leadership on organizational performance (Haque et al., 2024; Kanwal et al., 2025).

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY AND INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR

Social exchange theory develops trust in employees to create openness in the attitudes of employees by proving circumstances of readiness to listen and accept innovative ideas for enhancing organizational performance. (Li et al., 2024)

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY

Social exchange theory presents psychological safety to employees and eliminates the factor of fear and inadequate experiences to improve performance of the organization. (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY AND SPORTS PERFORMANCE

Social exchange theory provides incentives and inspiration through positive attitude of leadership, and it becomes obligation for employees to perform their best for enhancing performance of the organization (Wasono & Furinto, 2018; Siddique et al., 2025).

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP

Psychologist Brewer conceived the concept of inclusive leadership in 1991 explaining self-esteem, sense of belonging (belongingness) and sense of distinctiveness (uniqueness) (Brewer, 1991). Inclusive leadership behaviour is a source of motivation for employees (Nembhard & Edmondson, 2006). Inclusive leadership is open to listen new ideas, available and accessible for employees to consult on emerging professional issues to accomplish organizational goals through their innovative ideas (Carmeli et al., 2010). Inclusive leadership provides sense of belonging (belongingness) and sense of individuality (uniqueness) to team members for their involvement in decision making to augment organizational

performance (Randel et al., 2018).

INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR

Innovative work behaviour comprises various behaviours and actions of the employees to achieve organizational performance (Ajmal et al., 2024). It is a source of creating new innovative ideas to improve organizational innovation and attractiveness for sustainable competitive edge (Mursaleen et al., 2024).

PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY

Psychological safety was perceived in 1990, and it stipulates a safe psychological environment for employees and guarantees them to feel unrestricted and safe to express their concerns without any fear for performing challenging responsibilities of the organizational performance (Kahn, 1990). It allows employees that they can raise their voices without fear of adverse consequences (Lee & Seo, 2024).

SPORTS PERFORMANCE

Performance is the earmark of any leadership to complete organizational objectives, goals, mission, and vision. Sports performance foster's national identity, and UN has highlighted that sports are a powerful tool for achieving its seventeen sustainable development goals through sports optimistic influence on public health, economy of the country, social integration of diverse societies around the world (Bibi et al., 2025).

RESEARCH GAP

Literature review unveiled that effect of inclusive leadership on performance has been investigated in the fields of education (Vermeulen et al., 2022), higher education institutions (Ly, 2024), and in the perspective of digital industrial revolution (Karimi & Khawaja, 2024). Considering the literature review, it necessitates to explore the impact of inclusive leadership on performance with other mediating factors that affect performance (AlMunthiri et al., 2024). This investigation explores the influence of inclusive leadership on sports performance in the field of sports industry through mediating effects of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety through following four research gaps.

THEORETICAL RESEARCH GAP

Theoretical research gap is established where existent research theories, models and frameworks are incapable and lacking to describe a phenomenon and to meet the constraints of a research study. Numerous researches have been carried out to improve organizational performance with various variables whereas, no study has been conducted in Pakistan for measurement of inclusive leadership influence on sports performance with the mediating effects of innovative work behavior and psychological safety.

EMPIRICAL RESEARCH GAP

Empirical research gap defines the shortages of research work and non-availability of evidences for measuring sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. This study is an effort to find the empirical gap to determine performance of sports industry.

CONTEXTUAL RESEARCH GAP

Contextual gap describes research settings and contexts where investigations have not been carried out. Inclusive leadership has not been investigated it in the context of sports industry in Pakistan.

PRACTICAL RESEARCH GAP

Practical research gap describes the absence of previous research findings that have not been applied in practical and expert manner. (Usman et al., 2024). This study provides practical solutions to sports industry of Pakistan for improving sports performance at national and international levels.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework was instituted on the grounds of social exchange theory that can be assessed through quantitative research technique based on the Saunders Onion research model. Model presents inclusive leadership as independent variable, performance dependent variable, innovative work behaviour and psychological safety as mediating variables.

HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Impact of Inclusive Leadership in Enhancing Sports Performance

Inclusive leadership creates inclusive environment in the organization to generate innovative work behavior of the employees and psychological safety for accomplishing organizational performance (AlMunthiri, Bani-Melhem, et al., 2024). Leadership plays a pivotal role in improving psychological safety of players through well-being and listening to players' concerns for improving sports performance. (Hurst & Kavussanu, 2025). Therefore, first hypothesis is proposed

as.

H1: Inclusive leadership has a positive impact on sports performance.

Mediation Impact of Innovative Work Behaviour on the Relationship Between Inclusive Leadership and Sports Performance

Innovative work behaviour plays a important role in enhancing performance for achieving organizational goals (De Clerck et al., 2024). Innovative work behaviour in the fields of sports industry means the players' initiatives for origination and utilization of innovative ideas to achieve sports performance. Second hypothesis is proposed as:

H2: Innovative work behaviour positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance.

Mediation Impact of Psychological Safety on the Relationship Between Inclusive Leadership and Sports Performance

Researchers have investigated that psychological safety influences performance through inclusive leadership, and it provides security to its employees for communicating their innovative ideas without any fear (Carmeli et al., 2010). It is also supported that influence of employees with high level of psychological safety is positive between the organizational performance and job satisfaction (Kızrak, 2025). Therefore, third hypothesis is proposed as.

H3: Psychological safety positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Developed hypotheses of the study are appended below.

H1: Inclusive leadership has a positive impact on sports performance.

H2: Innovative work behaviour positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance.

H3: Psychological safety positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is a logical plan for collection of data and succeeding statistical analysis for findings of the study. Research design is based on Saunders Onion research model, and it defines research philosophy, research approach, research methodology, research strategy, time horizon and data collection for determining findings and conclusion (Melnikovas, 2018). Saunder's onion research model is considered suitable to conduct this research study in an organized manner for for results, findings, and conclusions (Mark Saunders & Paul Tosey, 2013). Partial Least squares Structural Equation Modeling PLS-(SEM) was utilized for statistical analysis to observe operational associations (Demir & Uşak, 2025). Positivism philosophy was used to find generalizable results and provision of statistical validation of hypotheses for formation of associations between inclusive leadership, innovative work behaviour, psychological safety, and sports performance variables.

RESEARCH APPROACH

Deductive research approach was used as it affiliates with the SET for determining research framework and development of hypotheses constructed on literature for testing through quantitative analysis of data (Bibi et al., 2025).

RESEARCH STRATEGY

Survey questionnaire was adopted for this quantitative research study to collect data from national players of sports organizations to find results, and study conclusion.

TIME HORIZON

Cross-sectional time horizon technique was utilized and cost effective (Slater & Hasson, 2025).

UNIT OF ANALYSIS

Unit of analysis is a sports player of national and international level belonging to any federation of Pakistan's Sports board or in any cricket club of Pakistan Cricket Board.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

National level player of any sport organization that is presently playing at national and international levels. (Slater & Hasson, 2025).

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Population comprises of sports players of 19 federations under PSB and cricket players under PCB. 20 sports organizations under PSB and cricket organization of PCB include Archery, Athletics, Badminton, Boxing, Football, Golf, Hockey, Kabaddi, Karate, Polo, Shooting, Rowing, Sailing, Squash, Swimming, Table Tennis, Taekwondo, Volleyball, Weightlifting and Cricket.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Snowball (for hidden population) sampling (Rifqi Azhary & Astuti Siregar, 2025) technique of non-probability sampling was applied to collect data from players of 20 sports organizations affiliated with PSB and PCB.

SAMPLE SIZE

Overall population of sports players belonging to 41 federations under PSB and PCB cannot be established due to non-availability of data and records pertaining to national players; therefore, sample comprised of 385 sports players as per the William G Cochran formula.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL / INSTRUMENTS / QUESTIONNAIRE

434 questionnaires were delivered in person for face-to-face feedback and quick response. 49 responses were rejected due to overwriting, double response, and cuttings. Questionnaire was adapted for the following research constructs.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Survey questionnaire was not emailed or sent by courier to the national players and presented for face to face for natural response through snowball sampling. Sports players of twenty (20) sports as of the sample were considered at Rawalpindi, Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore, Faisalabad, and Sargodha.

Variables	Elements	Sources
Inclusive Leadership	09	Carmeli, 2010
Psychological Safety	05	Edmondson (1999)
Innovative work behaviour	09	Scott and Bruce (1994)
Sports Performance	06	Seungbak Lee (2024)

DATA ANALYSIS

Smart PLS was employed for determining validity and the reliability of the data. Variance-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was reviewed using the partial least squares path modeling method. Statistical analyses were conducted through multivariate linear regression technique for better understanding and conception of the complex relationships among multiple dependent and independent variables. (Amira Wali Omer, 2025).

PILOT STUDY

Pilot study was regulated to check the content validity of the research instrument for collection of research data (Mohamad et al., 2024). Pilot study comprised 87 national sports players of various games from Rawalpindi, Islamabad, Sargodha, Faisalabad, Lahore, and Karachi to ensure participation of maximum sports regions.

RESEARCH ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Participation in the survey was volunteer, and consent of leadership was obtained from Secretary General Pakistan Olympic Association and Director of sports federations before soliciting response from the players of sports industry.

STRUCTURE EQUATION MODELING (SEM)

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is employed for analysis of data to investigate variables of the study. SEM technique via Smart PLS 4.0 was applied for analysis of the data. Use of Smart PLS 4.0 in the study guarantees correct calculations of both direct and indirect effects and improving the goodness of the model for causal links between core constructs.

DEMOGRAPHICS OF THE POPULATION

Demographics of the population express characteristics of the population like gender, age and playing experience of the players. Male national players in the study sample consisted of 250 national players, making 64.9% of the sample population and female participation in the sample was 135 females that made 35.1 % of the sample.

Data Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Inclusive Leadership (IL)	0.904	0.906	0.922	0.567
Innovative Work Behaviour (IB)	0.876	0.877	0.901	0.503
Psychological Safety (PS)	0.598	0.643	0.780	0.545
Sports Performance (SP)	0.751	0.754	0.833	0.501

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceed the minimum acceptable limit of 0.50, signifying adequate convergent validity. Overall, results approve that the measurement model possesses both strong reliability and convergent validity. Therefore, constructs used in this study, IL, IWB, PS, and SP, are examined with high precision and stability, establishing a solid foundation for subsequent structural model analysis. Results have been enlisted in Table 4.3

Discriminant Validity

	Inclusive Leadership	Innovative Work Behaviour	Psychological Safety	Sports Performance
Inclusive Leadership (IL)	0.753			
Innovative Work Behaviour (IB)	0.767	0.709		
Psychological Safety (PS)	0.584	0.608	0.738	
Sports Performance (SP)	0.406	0.548	0.502	0.708

DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

Results of the discriminant validity assessment, using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, indicate that all constructs meet the required threshold, confirming that each is empirically distinct from the others. Square roots of the AVE values, represented along the diagonal of the matrix, are higher than the corresponding inter-construct correlations in their respective rows and columns. Specifically, the diagonal values for IL (0.753), IWB (0.767), PS (0.584), and SP (0.406) exceed their correlations with other constructs. For instance, IL's correlation with IWB (0.709), PS (0.608), and SP (0.548) remains below or equal to its own square root of AVE, while similar patterns are observed for IWB, PS, and SP. Each construct accounts for more variance among its indicators than among those of other constructs, thereby establishing discriminant validity. Findings verify that IL, IWB, PS, and SP are conceptually and statistically distinct, ensuring that the measurement model is both reliable and valid for subsequent structural analysis.

MULTICOLLINEARITY

Results of the collinearity assessment based on the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values indicate that multicollinearity is not a concern among the measurement items of IL, IWB, PS, and SP. All VIF values fall well below the conservative threshold of 3.3 (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2006) and the more liberal cut-off value of 5.0 (Legate et al., 2024), confirming that each indicator contributes uniquely to its respective construct without significant redundancy.

R-SQUARE VALUES

From the R^2 results, the structural model explains a high proportion of the variation in the endogenous constructs, indicating strong predictive power. More precisely, R^2 for IWB is equal to 0.588, meaning that about 58.8% of the variance in IWB can be accounted for by its exogenous predictors. Likewise, PS has an R^2 of 0.339, indicating that the independent constructs explain 33.9% of the variance in OCTA. Finally, the SP R^2 value is 0.351, indicating that the model explains 35.1% of the variance.

R-square values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Innovative Work Behaviour (IWB)	0.588	0.587
Psychological Safety (PS)	0.341	0.339
Sports Performance (SP)	0.351	0.346

PATH ANALYSIS

Structural model findings indicate that all the hypothesized paths are significantly supported, providing solid theoretical and empirical evidence for our proposed model. The coefficient for the path from Inclusive Leadership \rightarrow Innovative Work Behaviour is positive and significant ($\beta = 0.767$, $t = 32.088$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that an increase in IL substantially increases IWB. The change in IL in PS is also significant ($\beta = 0.584$, $t = 16.712$, $p = 0.000$), indicating the strong role of IL in promoting PS in the model. The direct path from IL to SP is not significant, ($\beta = -0.128$, $t = 1.8$, $p = 0.072$). Thus, "H1 is not supported" in this research study.

Path Analysis

Hyp	Relationship	Coefficient (β)	Std. Dev	t-Statistics	p-values
H1	IL \rightarrow SP	-0.128	0.071	1.80	0.07

Inclusive Leadership=IL, Sports Performance=SP

MEDIATION ANALYSIS

Mediating effects analysis determined that both the mediator's psychological safety and innovative work behaviour mediate the impact of inclusive leadership significantly on sports performance. The indirect impact of inclusive leadership on sports performance through psychological safety is positive and proven statistically significant ($\beta = 0.198$, $t = 5.764$, $p < 0.001$), demonstrating that leaders who enhance inclusiveness improve athletes' perceptions of psychological safety, which in turn significantly improves sports performance. Similarly, the mediation of innovative work behaviour validates a strong indirect effect ($\beta = 0.341$, $t = 6.579$, $p < 0.001$), augmenting that inclusive leadership significantly improves sports performance through innovative work behaviour. Overall, results of the study approve the presence of robust mediating mechanisms, highlighting that inclusive leadership contributes positively to improve sports performance through mediation of psychological safety and innovative work behaviour.

Mediation analysis for Hypotheses testing

Hyp	Relationship	Coefficient (β)	Std. Dev	t-Statistics	p-values
H2	IL \rightarrow PS -SP	0.198	0.034	5.764	0.000
H3	IL \rightarrow IWB-P	0.341	0.052	6.579	0.000

*Inclusive Leadership=IL, Psychological Safety=PS, Sports Performance=SP, Innovative Work Behavior= IWB

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

Study was planned to investigate the "influence of inclusive leadership in improving sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behavior and psychological safety". Literature review indicates that inclusive leadership has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance. It is proved by scholars that sports leadership is an exceptionally critical element for enhancing sports performance and provision of sports platforms along with facilities to enhance sports performance at national and international levels (Shollen & Hanold, 2025).

H1: Inclusive leadership has a positive impact on sports performance

First hypothesis states that "inclusive leadership has a positive impact on sports performance". This hypothesis is not supported by statistical analysis of the research data and proves that inclusive leadership is not being exercised in sports industry, and it has a significant negative impact on players' sports performance. This negative and significant direct relationship between inclusive leadership and sports performance is a matter of concern and requires careful explanation of the findings. This negative impact of inclusive leadership is contrary to studies that have proved positive impact of inclusive leadership on organizational performance. Evidence of results clearly indicate that inclusive leadership is not being exercised in sports industry of Pakistan, resulting devastating performances at national and international levels. It is also evident from the negative impact of inclusive leadership on sports performance that players do not have the feeling of psychological safety and they are not even permitted to exhibit their capabilities of innovative work behaviour to enhance their professional sports performance. Therefore, fostering inclusive leadership emerges not merely as a theoretical recommendation but as a practical imperative for transforming Pakistan's sports culture and unlocking its potential for national and international success.

H2: Innovative work behaviour positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance

Second hypothesis of the study states that "Innovative work behaviour positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance". This hypothesis of the study is supported by statistical analysis of the research data and findings of this study revealed that innovative work behaviour has a significant positive mediation effect between inclusive

leadership and sports performance (Mohamad et al., 2024). Findings of this study advise that inclusive leadership is most effective when it provides inclusive environment to sports players for exhibition of their innovative capabilities to improve their sports performance. Innovative work behavior plays a pivotal role through inclusive leadership for improving sports performance at national and international sports competitions.

H3: Psychological safety positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance

Third hypothesis states that “Psychological safety positively mediates between inclusive leadership and sports performance” and proposed hypothesis is also established by results of the study with the significant positive mediation of psychological safety between inclusive leadership and sports performance. Scholars have confirmed in various studies that inclusive leadership is predictor of psychological safety and succeeding improvement of organizational performance through positive mediation of psychological safety. Psychological safety in sports industry persuades sports players to use their ideas for excellence in sports performance (Van Herck & Nordin-Bates, 2025).

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

Study provides specific grounds for other organizations to investigate these variables for improvement of their organizational performance. Study provides the following four (4) implications.

THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

Theoretical model of the study contributes to improve literature on inclusive leadership and sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behavior and psychological safety. It also adds in the literature that innovative work behavior and psychological safety positively mediate the relationship inclusive leadership and sports performance. This rationale of the study model necessitates investigation with the other variables to enhance organizational performance.

EMPIRICAL IMPLICATIONS

Positive relationship between inclusive leadership and psychological safety provided empirical evidence that inclusive leadership has a positive impact on sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. Empirical implications of the study provide predictions that can be used for validation of various research models through findings of the research this study.

CONTEXTUAL IMPLICATIONS

study findings will be applicable to improve performance of other organizations in different contexts. Contextual implications of the study present predictions that can be used for examining various research models through results of this research study in different contextual environments.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Practical implications include actionable findings for the Pakistan sports industry and other sports organizations to increase their sports performance. The study also provides guidance to the sports industry leadership for formulation of sports policies to meet international sports standards at global level.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF THE STUDY

Limitations and future directions are summarized for dissertations of future scholars.

EXPANDED CONTEXTUAL RESEARCH STUDIES

Firstly, study focused only on the sports industry whereas, studies may be carried out in other business and industrial organizations like agriculture, technology and health care. Secondly data was collected only from national level players, whereas the input of foreign players would have also been valuable for validity of the study findings. Thirdly data has been collected from only 19 sports federations and cricket board players, whereas data may be collected from all 41 sports federations. This application will generalize the results for comparison of findings in different research settings.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Study explored the influence of inclusive leadership on sports performance with the mediation of innovative work behaviour and psychological safety, whereas other variables like job autonomy and job security may also be used as mediators for investigation of the same relationships in sports industry and other research investigation.

LONGITUDINAL STUDIES

This study was carried out on cross-sectional design to examine the impact of inclusive leadership in enhancing sports performance through innovative work behaviour and psychological safety, whereas longitudinal studies may be conducted in the sports industry to determine the longtime influence of inclusive leadership in enhancing sports performance with the same variables.

QUALITATIVE INSIGHTS

This research study was carried out by a research questionnaire. Future research studies may be carried out through qualitative or mixed research methods having interviews of the players for better insight into the relationship between sports leadership and sports performance.

CROSS-CULTURAL COMPARISONS

This study was carried out in the sports industry of Pakistan. Further research studies may be conducted to find the influence of inclusive leadership on sports performance with the same variable across the cultures around the world for better understanding of the research variables and validation of this study findings.

CONCLUSION

Leadership plays an important role in the achievement of any organization and inclusive leadership has been acknowledged as a significant factor for improving performance of the sports industry. Seeing the effectiveness of inclusive leaders in various public and private universities of Pakistan, bank sector, health organizations, it also needs to be given significant importance in sports industry for improving its performance at national and international levels

through innovative work behavior and psychological safety. Findings of this study proved that inclusive leadership is not being practiced in sports industry of Pakistan and resulting poor sports performance at national and international level sports competitions. Outcomes of the study will also be useful to project soft image of the country to achieve its diplomatic goals. Study will also provide effective guidelines to policy makers for preparation of policies and strategies to enhance sports performance at global competitions. Considering the effectiveness of inclusive leaders, it needs to be given importance in sports industry to enhance performance of sports players through innovative work behaviour and psychological safety. It is confirmed and established by the scholars that sports are more capable of sustainable development than the sustainable development of sports.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, S., Audi, M., & Ali, A. (2025). Leaders Versus Laggards: ESG Performance, Valuation Premiums, and the Cost of Capital. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*, 3(3), 1899-1912.
- Ait Soussane, J., & Ibourk, A. (2024). Does hosting FIFA World Cup attract inward FDI? An empirical investigation using sectoral panel data of 12 countries. *International Journal of Event and Festival Management*.
- Ajmal, M., Sareet, Z., & Islam, A. (2024). Unleashing innovation through employee voice behavior in the hotel industry: the impact of ambidextrous leadership on innovative work behavior. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*.
- Ali, A., & Rehman, H. U. (2015). Macroeconomic instability and its impact on gross domestic product: an empirical analysis of Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 285-316.
- AlMunthiri, O., Bani-Melhem, S., Mohd-Shamsudin, F., & Al-Naqbi, S. A. (2024). Does leading with inclusiveness promote innovative behaviours? Examining the role of work engagement and psychological safety. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*.
- Asare, M. K., & Schnitzer, M. (2024). Does a coach's reputation affect an athlete's creativity in team sports? *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*.
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. (1989). Social Identity Theory and the Organization. In *Source*:
- Bergkvist, L., & Skeiseid, H. (2024). Sportswashing: exploiting sports to clean the dirty laundry. *International Journal of Advertising*, 1-19.
- Bibi, M., Jan, S. H., Saleem, M., & Khan, A. (2025). Integrating Sustainability into Human Resource Practices: A Comprehensive Model for Enhancing Organizational Performance in Pakistan. *Sciences Studies*, 3, 2025.
- Brewer, M. B. (1991). The social self: On being the same and different at the same time. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 17(5), 475-482.
- Campillo-Sánchez, J., Borrego-Balsalobre, F. J., Díaz-Suárez, A., & Morales-Baños, V. (2025). Sports and Sustainable Development: A Systematic Review of Their Contribution to the SDGs and Public Health. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 17, Number 2). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17020562>
- Carmeli, A., Reiter-Palmon, R., & Ziv, E. (2010a). Inclusive leadership and employee involvement in creative tasks in the workplace: The mediating role of psychological safety. *Creativity Research Journal*, 22(3), 250-260.
- Cropanzano, R., & Mitchell, M. S. (2005). Social exchange theory: An interdisciplinary review. *Journal of Management*, 31(6), 874-900.
- De Clerck, T., Van Doren, N., & De Bock, T. (2024). The role of leadership in group cohesion: insights from sport club volunteering. *Organization Management Journal*.
- Demir, S., & Uşak, M. (2025). Analyzing the Implementation of PLS-SEM in Educational Technology Research: A Review of the Past 10 Years. In *SAGE Open* (Vol. 15, Number 2). SAGE Publications Inc.
- Erdilnita, U., & Ma'mun, A. (2024). *The Role of Sports Participation on Social Skill Development in Early Childhood and Adolescence* (pp. 160-181).
- Huang, M., & Yongquan, T. (2025). Tech-driven excellence: A quantitative analysis of cutting-edge technology impact on professional sports training. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 41(1).
- Hurst, P., & Kavussanu, M. (2025). Authentic leadership and well-being in sport: the mediating role of psychological safety and the moderating role of interpersonal violence. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*.
- Hurst, P., Chatziefstathiou, D., & Stirling, A. (2025). British junior elite track and field athletes' experience of maltreatment, psychological safety, and subjective vitality. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 43(9), 906-914.
- Jiang, Y. (2024). How Large-Scale Sports Events Can Promote Urban Economic Development: Taking the Hangzhou Asian Games as an Example. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 193, 01023.
- Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological Conditions of Personal Engagement and Disengagement at Work. In *Source: The Academy of Management Journal* (Vol. 33, Number 4).
- Kanwal, F., Ahmad, K., & Ali, A. (2025). Exploring the impact of ethical leadership, workplace fun, and work-life balance on employee performance in the service sector. *Qualitative Research Journal for Social Studies*, 2(2), 390-406.
- Karimi, H., & Khawaja, S. (2024). Inclusive Leadership. *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, 8(6), 2403-2414.
- Khan, W., & Wali, R. (2020). Assessing the impact of a comprehensive capacity building program on educational leadership and teaching performance in public and private sectors. *Journal of Business and Economic Options*, 3(3), 91-99.
- Krambia Kapardis, M., & Levi, M. (2023). Fraud and corruption in football: lessons from a survey of match-fixing in Cyprus. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 30(4), 891-907.
- Lee, S. E., & Seo, J. K. (2024). Effects of nurse managers' inclusive leadership on nurses' psychological safety and

- innovative work behavior: The moderating role of collectivism. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*.
- Legate, A. E., Hair, J. F., Chretien, J. L., & Risher, J. J. (2023). PLS-SEM: Prediction-oriented solutions for HRD researchers. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 34(1), 91–109.
- Legate, A. E., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2024). PLS-SEM: A method demonstration in the R statistical environment. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 35(4), 501–529.
- Lodhi, R. N., Asif, M., Abdikarimova, A., & Shahzad, M. F. (2024). Impact of innovation and sustainability on green entrepreneurship: a bibliometric exploration. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*.
- Lundqvist, C., Camps, J., Vertommen, T., Barker-Ruchti, N., & Kolbeinsson, Ö. (2025). Toxic leadership in high-performance sports and its consequences for mental health and performance: a scoping review. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*.
- Marc, A. (2025). Corporate Governance and Profitability: Evidence from Leadership Role Segregation and Gender Diversity in Dubai. *Journal of Business and Economic Options*, 8(3), 24–34.
- Mark saunders, & Paul Tosey. (2013). *The Layers of Research Design 2013*.
- Marwat, N. M., Khan, M. A., Javed, A., Shah, M. I., & Ullah, H. (2020). *Perception of Spectators and Athletes About Down-Swing of Sport in Pakistan*.
- Mazahir, I., Muhammad, A. F., & Yaseen, S. (2020). Examining sports/cricket diplomacy as a tool to instigate political interests: A comparative analysis of media portrayal of cricketing relations between India and Pakistan. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 6118–6160.
- Melnikovas, A. (2018). Towards an explicit research methodology: Adapting research onion model for futures studies. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 23(2), 29–44.
- Mohamad, N. I., Rahman, I. A., Hasan, H., & Sanusi, S. (2024). Unlocking proactivity at work: Exploring the mediating role of green motivation between managerial coaching in training programmes and employee green behaviour. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(7).
- Molm, L. D. (2015). Homans's vision of social exchange. In *George C. Homans* (pp. 135–156). Routledge.
- Murray, S. (2018). *Sports diplomacy: Origins, theory and practice*. Routledge.
- Mursaleen, M., Shahzad, A., Parveen, M., & Aslam, M. S. (2024). Contribution of Twenty-first Century Leadership to the Employees' Innovative Work Behavior: A Systematic Literature Review. *Administrative and Management Sciences Journal*, 2(2), 111–124.
- Mwamba, J. (2023). Effective Leadership in Change Management: Ensuring Success in Organizational Transformation. *Journal of Policy Options*, 6(1), 28–38.
- Nordin, A., Jamal, A., Hussin, N. Z. H. M., Abdullah, M. Z., & Saadun, S. J. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Patriotism, Volunteerism and Perceived Empowerment on Community Engagement in Sports Events. *Information Management and Business Review*, 15(3 (SI)), 490–496.
- Piggott, L. V., Hovden, J., & Knoppers, A. (2024). Why organization studies should care more about gender exclusion and inclusion in sport organizations. In *Sociological thinking in contemporary organizational scholarship* (pp. 201–226). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Pitts, B. G. (2020). Technology and sport marketing. In *Managing Sport Across Borders* (pp. 127–146). Routledge.
- Randel, A. E., Galvin, B. M., Shore, L. M., Ehrhart, K. H., Chung, B. G., Dean, M. A., & Kedharnath, U. (2018). Inclusive leadership: Realizing positive outcomes through belongingness and being valued for uniqueness. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28(2), 190–203.
- Rifqi Azhary, M., & Astuti Siregar, S. (2025). Risky Sexual Behavior Practices in the Former Pucuk Jambi Localization and Distribution of Commercial Sex Workers (CSWs) in Jambi Province: A Qualitative Study with Snowball Approach. In *Proceedings Academic Universitas Jambi* (Vol. 1, Number 2).
- Rodriguez, F., & Rodrik, D. (2000). Trade policy and economic growth: a skeptic's guide to the cross-national evidence. *NBER Macroeconomics Annual*, 15, 261–325.
- Senturk, M. (2023). Transformational leadership and cultural dynamics in the pharmaceutical sector. *Journal of Policy Options*, 6(3), 1–8.
- Shollen, S. L., & Hanold, M. (2025). Game Changers: Leadership Lessons From Popular Sport Icons. *New Directions for Student Leadership*, 2025(185), 25–31.
- Siddique, A., Ali, A., & Audi, M. (2025). Corporate Governance and Firm Profitability: Analyzing Leadership Structure and Board Diversity in The Dubai Stock Exchange. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*, 3(2), 1166–1176.
- Şimşek, A., & Devocioğlu, S. (2025). The Future of Technology at Mega Sports Events. *Türkiye Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 9(1), 48–66.
- Slater, P. (2025). Fundamentals of Quantitative Research Methods in Mental Health Nursing. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, 32(2), 457–460.
- Slater, P., & Hasson, F. (2025). Data Measurement, Instruments and Sampling. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, 32(3), 680–685.
- Smith, A., Hachen, S., Colangelo, J., Buadze, A., & Liebrez, M. (2023). Mental health resources and initiatives from European national cycling federations: Insights on policy and practice. *Sports Psychiatry: Journal of Sports and Exercise Psychiatry*.
- Tokay, B., & Akil, M. (2025). Tactical-game and technical approach: the importance of sport type and method in

- developing metacognitive control and awareness in school going children. *Current Psychology*.
- Torres-Mancera, R. (2025). Female leadership for sustainability: green, cultural and social impact of the world's best sportswomen. *European Public and Social Innovation Review*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.31637/epsir-2025-1361>
- Usman, M., Alqassimi, O., Nusairi, A. M. A., Abul, O., & Hussain, S. A. (2024). Foregrounding why and when inclusive leadership triggers customer stewardship in hospitality organizations. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, (ahead-of-print).
- Vermeulen, M., Kreijns, K., & Evers, A. T. (2022). Transformational leadership, leader–member exchange and school learning climate: Impact on teachers' innovative behaviour in the Netherlands., 50(3), 491–510.
- Wasono, L. W., & Furinto, A. (2018). The effect of digital leadership and innovation management for incumbent telecommunication company in the digital disruptive era. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology(UAE)*, 7(2), 125–130.
- Willis, O. (2000). Sport and development: the significance of Mathare Youth Sports Association. *Canadian Journal of Development Studies/Revue Canadienne d'études Du Développement*, 21(3), 825–849.
- Yilmaz, O., & Dertli, Ş. (2025). *International Journal of Sport Culture and Science The Development of Sports and Politics Publications Over Time*.
- Zbiljić, G., Perović, A., & Đurić, Z. (2025). International organizations, sport and sustainable development: the role in the implementation of the 2030 agenda. *Menadžment u Sportu*, 16(XVI, issue I), 112–131.